

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

M.Asanova

THE EPISODE OF MURATBAY NIZANOV'S ARTISTIC WORK "ASHIQ
BOLMAĞAN KIM BAR"

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/YANVAR

HONORED
MENTION

YOUR
SEAL